

ANNEX FOR:

Paoli R., Romagnoli F., Carnevale Miino M., Baltrocchi A. P. D., and Torretta V. 2025. Cascade Biorefinery of *Furcellaria lumbricalis* Macroalgae: Social Impact and Integration into a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

Summary

This supporting material provides detailed information on the reference scale used for the Social Life Cycle Assessment analysis and the panel of experts selected for the questionnaire submission. The questionnaires are instead reported separately as S1 and S2 files.

Moreover, the initial values of the LCA and LCC, as well as the scheme for the alternative biorefinery scenarios (AAp1 and AAp2), are proposed.

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1. REFERENCE SCALE USED FOR THE SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Below are reported reference scales created to quantify the answers provided by the experts into risk-quantitative values. They are divided by the 4 stakeholders selected.

- **Workers**

Health and safety

Scale level	Stakeholder category: WORKERS Impact subcategory: HEALTH AND SAFETY
+2	There are no risks for workers of the processes under analysis to be exposed to accidents/damages for health and safety as well as to carry out strenuous activities.
+1	There is a low risk for workers of the processes under analysis to be exposed to accidents/damages to health and safety as well as to carry out strenuous activities.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	There is a medium risk for workers of the processes under analysis to be exposed to accidents/damages to health and safety as well as to carry out strenuous activities.
-2	There is a very high risk for workers of the processes under analysis to be exposed to accidents/damages to health and safety as well as to carry out strenuous activities.

Working hours

Scale level	Stakeholder category: WORKERS Impact subcategory: WORKING HOURS
+2	There is no risk . 0% of workers exceed 40-48 hours per week.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	There is a medium risk . From 0% to <50% of workers exceed 40-48 hours per week.
-2	There is a very high risk . More than 50% of workers exceed 40-48 hours per week.

Social benefits/social security

Scale level	Stakeholder category: WORKERS Impact subcategory: SOCIAL BENEFITS/SOCIAL SECURITY
+2	There are no risks . The workers have more than 6 social benefits.
+1	There is a low risk . The workers have between 2 and 6 social benefits.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	There is a medium risk . The workers have only 1 or 2 benefits.
-2	There is a very high risk . The workers do not have any social benefits.

- **Local community**

Safe and healthy living conditions

Scale level	Stakeholder category: LOCAL COMMUNITY Impact subcategory: SAFE AND HEALTHY LIVING CONDITIONS
+2	The presence of the process under analysis does not increase the perception of the risk of affecting the local living conditions.
+1	The presence of the process under analysis slightly increases the perception of the risk of affecting local living conditions.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The presence of the process under analysis increases the perception of the risk of affecting local living conditions.
-2	The presence of the process under analysis highly increases the perception of the risk of affecting local living conditions.

Local economic development

Scale level	Stakeholder category: LOCAL COMMUNITY Impact subcategory: LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT
+2	The presence of the processes under analysis could highly contribute to the development of the local economy by workforce hired locally, as well as prioritizing buying goods and services from local suppliers, and by the development of “satellite activities”.
+1	The presence of the processes under analysis could positively contribute to the development of the local economy.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The presence of the processes under analysis has a low contribution to economic development.
-2	The presence of the processes under analysis has a very low contribution to economic development

- **Consumers**

Health and safety

Scale level	Stakeholder category: CONSUMERS Impact subcategory: HEALTH AND SAFETY
+2	The presence of the processes under analysis could highly contribute to the development of zero hunger, good health & well-being, and responsible consumption & production practices
+1	The presence of the processes under analysis could positively contribute to the development of zero hunger, good health & well-being, and responsible consumption & production practices
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The presence of the processes under analysis has a low contribution to the development of zero hunger, good health & well-being, and responsible consumption & production practices
-2	The presence of the processes under analysis has a very low contribution to the development of zero hunger, good health & well-being, and responsible consumption & production practices

Transparency

Scale level	Stakeholder category: CONSUMERS Impact subcategory: TRANSPARENCY
+2	The selected “actor” highly contributes to promoting transparency using practices like certification standards, labels, and special indices. Moreover, it provides sustainability reports based on standardized methodology such as life cycle impact assessment.
+1	The selected “actor” positively contributes to promoting transparency using practices like certification standards, labels, and special indices.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The selected “actor” has a low contribution to promoting transparency using practices like certification standards, labels, and special indices. Moreover, it provides sustainability reports based on standardized methodology such as life cycle impact assessment.
-2	The selected “actor” has a very low contribution to promoting transparency using practices like certification standards, labels, and special indices. Moreover, it provides sustainability reports based on standardized methodology such as life cycle impact assessment.

- **Social indicators for value chain actors**

Fair competition

Scale level	Stakeholder category: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS Impact subcategory: FAIR COMPETITION
+2	The selected “actor” highly contributes to promoting fair competition. Conducting competitive activities in a fair way and in compliance with preventing anti-competitive behavior, anti-trust, or monopoly practices.
+1	The selected “actor” positively contributes to promoting fair competition. Conducting competitive activities in a fair way and in compliance with preventing anti-competitive behavior, anti-trust, or monopoly practices.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The selected “actor” has a low contribution to promoting fair competition. Conducting competitive activities in a fair way and in compliance with preventing anti-competitive behavior, anti-trust, or monopoly practices.

-2	The selected “actor” has a very low contribution to promoting fair competition. Conducting competitive activities in a fair way and in compliance with preventing anti-competitive behavior, anti-trust, or monopoly practices.
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Promoting social responsibility

Scale level	Stakeholder category: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS Impact subcategory: PROMOTING SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY
+2	The selected “actor” highly contributes to promoting social responsibility among its suppliers and through its own actions. These measures include monitoring (to consider human rights records when selecting suppliers), auditing, and training efforts.
+1	The selected “actor” positively contributes to promoting social responsibility among its suppliers and through its own actions. These measures include monitoring (to consider human rights records when selecting suppliers), auditing, and training efforts.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The selected “actor” has a low contribution to promoting social responsibility among its suppliers and through its own actions. These measures include monitoring (to consider human rights records when selecting suppliers), auditing, and training efforts.
-2	The selected “actor” has a very low contribution to promoting social responsibility among its suppliers and through its own actions. These measures include monitoring (to consider human rights records when selecting suppliers), auditing, and training efforts.

Wealth distribution

Scale level	Stakeholder category: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS Impact subcategory: WEALTH DISTRIBUTION
+2	The selected “actor” highly contributes to the wealth distribution among the supply chain using contract instruments, the creation of the interbranch organization, and the definition of a fair price for the products.
+1	The selected “actor” positively contributes to the wealth distribution among the supply chain using contract instruments, the creation of the interbranch organization, and the definition of a fair price for the products.
0	There is not a shared position of the experts, or there is not enough data available.
-1	The selected “actor” has a low contribution to the wealth distribution among the supply chain using contract instruments, the creation of the interbranch organization, and the definition of a fair price for the products.

-2

The selected “actor” **has a very low contribution** to the wealth distribution among the supply chain using contract instruments, the creation of the interbranch organization, and the definition of a fair price for the products.

2. PANEL OF EXPERT SELECTED FOR THE SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Name and Surname	Affiliation	Definition of the choice
Tanel Ilmjärv	Vetik OU	Tanel Ilmjärv is the CEO of VETIK OÜ, an Estonian company specializing in harvesting <i>Furcellaria lumbricalis</i> and testing the extraction of valuable compounds.
Joseph Santhi Pechsiri	Swedish University of Agricultural Science	Joseph Santhi Pechsiri specializes in Ecology and Environmental Systems Research, focusing on photosynthetic aquatic biomass. He applies Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and systems modeling to assess environmental performance within an Industrial Ecology context on different macroalgae systems.
Jean-Baptise Thomas	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	Jean-Baptiste Thomas focuses on developing a resilient, sustainable, and low-carbon blue bioeconomy. His research includes multi-use at sea, blue food, and blue carbon projects, with expertise in optimizing supply chains from carbon, energy, and nutrient perspectives.
Alexander Monteiro Souza	Swedish University of Agricultural Science	Alexander Monteiro Souza specializes in social life cycle assessment of bioenergy production and participatory research approaches, with experience in assessing social impacts in the sugarcane industry in Brazil and biofuel production in Southern Africa. He is part of the Brazilian Workgroup for Social Life Cycle Assessment.
Karīna Bāliņa	University of Latvia	Karīna Bāliņa is a researcher specializing in environmental impact assessment using life cycle modeling. She focuses on the sustainable use of marine seaweed in Latvia and Europe and is actively involved in international research projects on algae biorefinery and circular economy.
Andrea Cappelli	La Sapienza University	Andrea Cappelli is a full professor at La Sapienza University in Rome, specializing in LCA and the sustainable use of environmental resources, with expertise in life cycle thinking, macroalgae, and biogas production.
Bjarni Bjarnason	HYNDLA	Bjarni Bjarnason is the managing director of HYNDLA, an Icelandic company developing on-shore cultivation systems for macroalgae to produce high-quality and sustainable products.
Barry Antonio Costa-Pierce	University of New England	Barry Costa-Pierce is a professor with over 40 years of experience in marine and freshwater sciences. He is a pioneer of "Ecological Aquaculture" and contributed to the FAO's "Ecosystem Approach to

		Aquaculture." He has worked internationally and served as Editor-in-Chief of Aquaculture for 20 years.
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3. Results of LCA and LCC

Tables 1 and 2 report the results from the LCA and LCC analysis used in the LCSA with the TOPSIS method.

Table 1: Results of LCA readapted from (Romagnoli et al., 2024) and used in the TOPSIS analysis. Values are referred to per FU (1 ton of dry weight (DW) biomass of the red macroalgae *F. lumbricalis*).

	Global warming potential (GWP) (kg CO ₂ eq.)	Fine particulate matter formation (PM) (kg PM _{2.5})	Human carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic toxicity (HCCT) (kg 1.4-DCB)	Water consumption (WC) (m ³)
PrAp	1818.34	3.95	2342.54	40.87
AAp1	1841.98	5.77	4003.52	34.77
AAp2	618.89	1.93	1337.66	11.64

Table 2: Results of LCC readapted from (Paoli et al., 2025) and used in the TOPSIS analysis. Values are referred to per FU (2000 tons of dry weight (DW) biomass of the red macroalgae *F. lumbricalis*).

	Return of investment (ROI) (%)	Net Present Value (NPV) (€)	Internal Rate of Return (IRR) (%)	Profitability index (PI) (-)
PrAp	5147	82,437,798	559	40.05
AAp1	-336	-7,443,135	447	-3.61
AAp2	-209	-4,055,130	0	-1.97

4. Technological scheme of the alternative biorefinery designs

In figure 1 and 2 are reported the technological scheme for the single product extraction (AAp1) and three line extraction (AAp2).

Figure 1: Technological scheme of the *F. lumbricalis* harvesting, transport, and valorization in the biorefinery using the single-step approach (AAp1).

Figure 2: Technological scheme of the *F. lumbricalis* harvesting, transport, and valorization in the biorefinery using the three line approach (AAp2)

References:

- Paoli, R., Foadelli, C., Traversi, M., Tomasoni, G., Romagnoli, F., 2025. Economic Feasibility of *Furcellaria lumbricalis* Biorefinery Designs: A Life Cycle Cost Approach. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5153254>
- Romagnoli, F., Paoli, R., Arias, A., Entrena-Barbero, E., Ilmjärv, T., Elvevold, K., Moreira, M.T., 2024. *Furcellaria lumbricalis* macroalgae cascade biorefinery: a Life Cycle Assessment study in the Baltic Sea Region. *J Clean Prod* 478, 143861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.143861>